

THE PROBLEM OF MORAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE IN THE THEORY AND PRACTICE OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Moral feelings play a huge role in the sphere of morality. Any person, small or adult, implementing moral norms in his behavior or violating them, experiences certain feelings. Morality enshrines such concepts as “goodness,” “honor,” “conscience,” and “justice.” All these spiritual and moral concepts are evaluative in nature. In educating a person, it is important to ensure that moral education is not only understandable, but also becomes the goal of every person’s life. Morality, as the essential basis of the life of society, and morality, as a personal quality, are the subject of ethics, ethical education, and the moral culture of human relations is the basis of ethical culture. The content of morality is expressed in the form of norms and assessments that are universal, binding on all people, claim to be absolute, guide consciousness and regulate human behavior in all spheres of life - in work, in everyday life, in politics, in personal, family, intra-group, international, etc. relationships*

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In accordance with the NUP, we are obliged to educate highly moral people. Education of moral qualities in school has two interdependent goals: ensuring the process of socialization of the child as a citizen of society and supporting the process of individualization of the individual. The education of moral qualities has its own specifics and is revealed in the following aspects: - in content: the implementation of educational programs in various disciplines should be of interest to children and their parents; □ by form of organization: voluntary children's associations in the form of circles, schools, studios, clubs, theaters, ensembles, sections, scientific societies, etc.; □ by methods: the main way to cultivate the moral qualities of an educational organization is the formation of beliefs and outlook on life. This method includes conversation, dialogue, example, explanation, play and creativity [1-2].

When planning activities to form moral guidelines for children of primary school age, the teacher’s goal becomes the choice of methods and techniques of education. Methods for educating moral qualities are a pedagogical tool that performs the functions of organizing the process of moral development and improving the child’s personality, managing this process [3].

In the sphere of personal development, moral education of students should be ensured:

- readiness and ability for spiritual development, moral self-improvement, self-esteem, understanding the meaning of one’s life, individually responsible behavior;
- readiness and ability to realize creative potential in spiritual and objectively productive activities, social and professional mobility based on moral standards, continuous education and the universal spiritual and moral attitude of “becoming better”;

- strengthening morality based on freedom, will and spiritual national traditions, the internal attitude of the individual to act according to his conscience;
- the formation of morality as a person's conscious need for certain behavior, based on socially accepted ideas about good and evil, proper and unacceptable;
- development of conscience as a person's moral self-awareness, the ability to formulate one's own moral obligations, exercise moral self-control, demand from oneself the fulfillment of moral standards, and give moral self-evaluation of one's own and others' actions;
- acceptance by the individual of basic national values, national spiritual traditions;
- willingness and ability to express and defend one's public position, critically evaluate one's own intentions, thoughts and actions;
- the ability to take independent actions and actions based on moral choice, taking responsibility for their results, determination and persistence in achieving results;
- hard work, frugality, optimism in life, ability to overcome difficulties;
- awareness of the value of other people, the value of human life, intolerance to actions and influences that pose a threat to life, physical and moral health and spiritual safety of the individual, the ability to counteract them;

Purposeful influence on children, expansion of moral experience, organization of their life activities occurs exclusively through methods of instilling moral qualities. In the pedagogical literature, two main groups of methods of moral education are distinguished: - methods of forming the consciousness of the individual. The teacher verbally influences the emotional sphere of the child's personality in order to form concepts, beliefs, ideas, and ideas. This group of methods includes ethical conversations, stories, explanation, suggestion, persuasion; - methods that, in their totality, contribute to the organization of activities and the development of skills and habits of correct behavior in society. These include teaching methods and various types of exercises, instructions, incentives, educational situations [4].

Pedagogical activities take place both with the team as a whole, and there must also be individual forms with the child. If the result of the work done is the development of the personality of an individual child, then the goal will be achieved. The entire educational system is subordinated to this goal. The acceleration and deepening of the highly moral development of students depends directly on the teacher's preparedness and equipment with tasks aimed at developing moral qualities. Also, the teacher's ability to correctly and competently apply methods to create optimal conditions for their use. The forms and nature of moral education methods may vary depending on the school community. It is extremely important to rely on the opinions of students and consult with them.

Creating a team is not the main goal, it is just the most productive and effective way to form a child's personality. It is necessary for the child to feel the responsibility and necessity of the assignment and, most importantly, for the student to understand what is required of him to do. The indicator of morality is actions and actions, and not words, as many people think. Absolutely any type of activity (game, learning, communication, work) is important for understanding and mastering knowledge and norms of rules of behavior. The formation of personality in the learning process is ensured only by the focused work of the teacher. The function of these methods is the formation of moral ideas, definitions and, on their basis, the beliefs and moral orientation of the individual. Using the method of persuasion, the teacher forms moral concepts and ideas, guided by which students develop evaluative attitudes towards people's actions, correct judgments,

towards social events and towards themselves, master moral norms and rules of behavior in everyday life, in society, in their team [6].

With the help of a set of techniques that are chosen in accordance with the pedagogical situation, the style of teaching of the teacher, taking into account the age and individual distinctive features of a child of primary school age, the implementation of educational methods is carried out. The same methods of education take place using the same techniques. "Education techniques are ways of organizing various pedagogical situations that influence the thoughts and feelings of students, encouraging them to take positive actions and work on their shortcomings" [7]. A large number of various methods of education are presented in the pedagogical literature. V.S. Kukushin proposes dividing educational methods into two groups: creative and inhibitory. Inhibitory techniques help correct the child's behavior by awakening in him feelings of remorse, shame, and regret. Feeling unpleasant feelings in the process of realizing his actions, he expresses the desire to correct his own behavior. This group of techniques includes: hint, reproach, command, irony, etc. Creative techniques are aimed at developing new positive qualities in the child, such as gratitude, joy, inspiration, faith in one's abilities [9].

This group of techniques includes: attention, care, request, persuasion, encouragement, moral support, expression of faith in the child's strengths and abilities on the part of the teacher, etc. Such techniques help inspire the child and encourage him to correct his own behavior based on striving for the best. Most often, children's activities in the classroom are organized using the exercise method. This is repeated repetition of actions in order to form and consolidate skills and habits of behavior [8]. The success of using this method is determined by the child's manifestation of positive personal qualities in various contradictory life situations. Let us analyze the methods and corresponding techniques that are often used in the process of developing moral qualities in children of primary school age. The stimulation method allows you to influence the child's motivational sphere. Stimulation is a set of actions of the teacher that give impetus to stimulate thoughts, feelings and actions of students [11]. This method involves the creation of certain conditions that contribute to the emergence in children of a desire and motive to carry out any activity. The components of the incentive method are reward and punishment. To influence the child's intellectual sphere, the method of persuasion is used. The method implies a logical proof and explanation of any judgment or conclusion [10].

In the process of persuasion, the teacher describes the necessity and importance of moral concepts, explains the falsity and danger of misconceptions. When using this method, it is important that the child does not feel that an opinion is being imposed on him and that they are being raised. The persuasion method includes the following techniques: explanation, conversation, discussion. The most humane way of stimulation is encouragement. Encouragement helps children grow their determination in their capabilities and abilities. It can be carried out through words, gestures, facial expressions, evaluation, demonstration of the student's achievements in front of other people. Encouragement implies the arousal of positive emotions, instills confidence, and develops in children the desire to set and achieve new, more complex goals. Methods of encouragement: approval, praise, gratitude, presentation of honorary rights, rewarding. It is important to use encouragement in moderation so that it does not become the main, much less the only goal to which the student will direct all his efforts. The teacher must take into account the individual characteristics of each student when encouraging and ensure that the encouragement is

objective. The greatest fairness is provided by encouragement consistent with the opinion of the team.

Another component of the incentive method is punishment. The method is aimed at preventing and inhibiting undesirable actions of students by awakening feelings of guilt and repentance. Methods of punishment: remark, warning, reprimand, imposition of additional duties, deprivation or restriction of rights, expression of moral reproach, condemnation. Before using punishment, the teacher should evaluate its fairness and carefully consider the punishment so that it does not humiliate the child's dignity, but has a positive impact on his behavior. The influence on the emotional sphere of the child is carried out using the method of suggestion. The purpose of this method is to teach children to manage their own feelings and emotions, understand their own emotional state and identify the causes that cause it. Methods of demand and exercise (training) allow you to influence the child's volitional sphere. These methods instill in children initiative, perseverance, dedication, independence, self-confidence, and the ability to overcome difficulties. A pedagogical requirement is a way of directly encouraging children to take actions or actions aimed at improving behavior. A requirement is a specific task that a student must complete in the process of a particular activity. Depending on the form of the message, a distinction is made between direct and indirect demands. The conditions for a direct requirement are specificity, accuracy, certainty, and understandable formulation [6].

A direct demand should be made in a decisive, confident and convinced tone. Forms of direct demand: tactful instruction, order, instruction, instruction. An indirect requirement is a hidden motivation of the student to perform some action. Indirect requirement 28 is based on the interests, aspirations, and experiences of children. Forms of indirect demand: advice, request, hint, approval, etc. The method of behavior correction allows you to effectively influence the child's sphere of self-regulation. The method involves creating certain conditions under which the child will have a need to make changes in his behavior and attitude towards other people. The method can be carried out through comparing the student's actions with generally accepted norms of morality and ethics, analyzing the consequences of the student's actions, and reflecting on the actions of the characters in a literary work. The highest effectiveness is ensured by behavioral adjustments based on the teacher's personal example. In this case, the teacher must demonstrate to his students an example of impeccable moral behavior, indicators of which will be speech, manners, habits, actions, appearance and other factors. The teacher must keep in mind that at this age children have increased emotional sensitivity, so they easily expose the falsity, unnaturalness, and insincerity in the behavior of others.

The influence on the child's subject-practical sphere is carried out using the method of educational situations. The method is focused on the formation of a child's experience of moral behavior and the development of stable qualities necessary for a person to realize himself in society. When children are included in situations of moral choice, their moral position is formed, which is necessary for further entry into the social environment. Techniques of this method: game, dramatization, discussion, competition. B.T. Likhachev identifies means for instilling moral qualities. - Artistic media. In solving the problems of educating moral qualities, literature, fine arts, music are very important, as they contribute to the emotional coloring of cognizable moral phenomena. The most significant in the formation of moral qualities in a child of primary school age and the education of feelings are artistic means [11]. - Nature. Understanding nature forms in a child of primary school age humane feelings, to protect those who are weaker, and to take care

of their neighbors. - Play, work, learning, communication - that is, children's own activities. Typically, a younger student is busy studying or playing. And it is in this activity that the child learns in practice how to treat a peer morally and how immorally. The atmosphere in which the child is raised. It can be imbued with love, good attitude towards each other, or cruelty and misunderstanding. Only in an atmosphere of goodwill, warmth, and humanity can one develop a full-fledged personality and give the opportunity to reveal all the abilities and talents inherent in a child from birth. - The environment surrounding the child. The environment (family circle, teachers, relatives, peers) has a tremendous impact on the formation of his moral attitudes. It is the environment of ideas and behavior that surrounds the child that becomes the means of educating feelings [8].

Thus, we have come to the conclusion that methods and techniques for educating moral qualities are a pedagogical mechanism that performs the functions of organizing the process of moral education and improving the child's personality. I would like to note that a characteristic feature in the process of forming the moral education of junior schoolchildren is that all the methods used, without exception, teach children to independently analyze the material from the point of view of morality and morality, good and evil, based on their existing values.

Thus, the methods and techniques that contribute to the moral education of children are very diverse. A wide variety of methods and techniques provides the teacher with the opportunity to plan and effectively implement activities to form moral guidelines for students. When selecting methods and techniques, the teacher must take into account several conditions: - the purpose and current objectives of education; - age and individual personality characteristics of students; □ features of the social environment of students (relationships in the family, in the children's group); - level of professional skill of the teacher (those methods that the teacher knows in practice are selected); -planned results of applying the selected methods and techniques.

The historical progress of universal human culture is assessed by the degree of humanization of relations in society, the expansion of the scope of morality in people's lives. The school as a social institution of education can significantly help society if it considers the solution to this problem one of the most important tasks of the educational process.

When comprehending the problem of moral education, it is necessary to determine the actual sources of moral and immoral behavior of people, to find out what morality and moral standards of behavior are. In order to further consider the process of moral education, it is necessary to reveal its essence and give a theoretical justification for the concept of "moral education" through revealing the essence of such basic concepts of pedagogical science as "education", "morality", "morality", "ethics", "personality" ", "moral education", "ethical culture".

The main core in the overall system of comprehensive personal development is moral education. Moral education is a process aimed at the holistic formation and development of a child's personality, and involves the formation of his relationships to the Motherland, society, team, people, to work, his responsibilities and to himself. It is important to awaken in children the desire to notice what can be done to make life better.

The task of moral education is for teachers to transform the socially necessary requirements of society into internal incentives for the personality of each child, such as duty, honor, conscience, and dignity.

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